

HADI Study_Appendices Chapter 5 (5.5 to 5.9) Final Version

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Healthy Ageing Diet Study

PRE-WORKSHOP RESOURCE 04.06.25

Barbara Bray

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Co-design workshops

What you will do

In this co-design project, people with a range of skills and experience are invited to create food concepts that meet the fibre and protein needs of people aged 65 years and older.

It's called co-design because everyone involved will contribute their ideas to the final concepts.

The purpose of this workbook is to give you the background information for the co-design workshops.

Workshop session	Who	How long	Format
Ideation	Food experts	3 hours	In person
Validation	Older people	90 minutes	In person
Refinement	Food experts	90 minutes	Online
Summary	Food experts and academics	90 minutes	July w/c Mon 7 th or 14 th

01

Dietary needs of 65+

Older people's diets are not providing sufficient nutrients to maintain good health with ageing. Increasing the missing the nutrients is important to support healthspan.

02

Changing food behaviours

The food environment including access, availability and quality has a big impact on peoples behaviour in addition to knowledge and life changes

03

Solution

Designing nutritious foods that suit the tastes and existing diets of older people is one solution that stakeholders can work on.

Key Nutrients and foods

Fibre

Men currently reaching
21g, and women 18g
Daily recommended
target is 30g

Protein

Men currently having 79g
and the optimum is 95-
103g
Women having 66g and
the optimum is 80-86g

Folate

The current recommended target
of 200mcg. Both men
(335mcg) and women (300mcg)
reach more than.
The proposed target for older
people is 400mcg

Fruit and vegetables

Current daily intakes -
Women 340g and
Men 352g
Daily recommended
target is 400g

Foods commonly eaten by older people containing protein

Meat and meat products
Cereals and cereal products
Milk and milk products
Fish and fish dishes
Vegetables and potatoes
Eggs and egg dishes
Nuts and seeds

Top 10 foods commonly eaten by older people containing fibre

- Baked beans
- Chips
- Wholemeal bread
- Fried/roast potatoes
- Peas

- Breakfast cereals
- Pizza
- Brown bread
- Other potatoes
- Beans/pulses

Consumer avatars

To help generate the ideas, avatars of four people have been created. Each one has background information about their lifestyle, food behaviours, preferences and any barriers that they may experience in their environment.

Target consumers

Widow

Retired widow, with adult children, eats most meals alone or goes for lunch with friends

Couple

Meals are predominantly prepared by the wife and the husband assists with shopping.

Divorcee

Single man, works part-time and eats some meals with friends and neighbours. Limited cooking skills.

Widow, 77 years old Berkshire

Shopping

Does a monthly big shop in the supermarket
Smaller top-up shops during the week
Uses all supermarkets and small local ones like Co-op
Freshness, taste and quality is important

Cooking

Most of her food is raw veg and fruit, mainly apples.
Mainly uses microwave, hob or stockpot

Eating

Vegetarian meals
Breakfast - Porridge of oats and fruit. Lunch - boiled egg, toast, celery and carrot. Dinner - salad or stir-fry
Eats alone and occasionally eats lunch out with friends

Barriers

What is in her environment that impacts the quality of her diet?

Widow, 77 years old Berkshire

Does

Can't be bothered to cook since husband passed away

Says

Having gadgets to manage arthritis symptoms - eg jar openers are great

Thinks

Mediterranean dietary pattern is healthy.
Getting to the supermarket will be tricky when she stops driving

Feels

Doesn't feel like eating alot because of small appetite

Breakfast
Lunch
Dinner
Snacks

Couple, 66 years old, Berkshire

Shopping

Weekly supermarket shop
and mid-week top ups.

Cooking

The wife cooks and the
husband will assist.
Mainly vegetable based soups
and stews, Jollof rice and
plantain with meat.
They use the air fryer alot

Eating

Eat most meals together and their
adult children and grandchildren
may join them some evenings
They like takeaways but don't go
out to eat much

Barriers

Multi-generational
household and tend to
buy things to suit different
family members

Couple, 66 years old, Berkshire

Does

Wife decides what to buy and husband accompanies her to the supermarket.

They snack a lot and often have a drink and salty nuts after dinner

Says

Life is busy and sometimes a takeaway is an easy solution

Thinks

He thinks price is less important than quality and taste but she does like bargains

Feels

It's a struggle to cut down on sugary and fatty foods

Breakfast Lunch Dinner Snacks

Divorcee, 69 years old, N.Ireland

Shopping

Tesco and Lidl
Opts for low fat meat and
would use special offers if
he had already planned
to buy the product

Cooking

Would make a batch of mince to
have with potatoes or pasta.
Makes beans on toast
occasionally.
Uses the hob mainly, also cooks
baked fish

Eating

Enjoys pasta and curries
Goes to cafes and likes
traybakes and scone
Goes out for pizza with
friends occasionally

Barriers

Lacks the motivation to
eat better

Divorcee, 69 years old, N.Ireland

Does

Shops little and often
Eats with friends occasionally
Does not have enough fruit
and vegetables

Says

Sometimes misses eating
a cooked meal and just
has bread and ham

Thinks

Should get more variety
into his diet

Feels

Lacks discipline in staying
healthy

Breakfast Lunch Dinner Snacks

Workshops planner

There are 4 stages to the development of the final solution

Ideation

EXPERT PANEL

Validation

LAY PANEL

Refinement

EXPERT PANEL

Summary

ACADEMIC TEAM

Who are the experts?

We looked at who would have the relevant skills to support older people in the co-design process. The skills needed for this activity include: nutrition knowledge, food product development, food policy and health policy knowledge, understanding of the retail and marketing process and the food environment related to older people. The biographies of the chosen experts follow on the next few pages.

The KCL host

Dr Richard Siow is the Director of Ageing Research at King's (ARK), a cross-university consortium of researchers taking a multidisciplinary approach to better understand the mechanisms of ageing, improving health-span and the social and economic impact of ageing.

His research team focuses on the role of nutrigenomics and ageing on redox signalling in cardiovascular and cerebrovascular health and disease. He kindly offered to host the first co-design workshop of this series.

Ideation

**30
mins**

A team of experts

The facilitator will give out the target consumer profiles and ask the team to come up with ideas that they have on the food behaviours (shopping, cooking and eating) of these older consumers

**20
mins**

Ideas selection

Each participant will be given 5 sticky dots and asked to allocate them to one or more of the ideas that they feel would be most impactful

**10
mins**

Create insight statements

The group will then use the ideas to make insight statements about the target consumers. For example, the widow from Berkshire has a good breakfast but she does not have enough protein in it.

How might we?

The group will then turn the insight statements into into ‘how might we questions’. For example, how might we get the widow to increase her protein intake at breakfast?

Brainstorm

The facilitator will brief participants on the rules of the brainstorm to encourage a flow of ideas without restriction. The team will be split into sub-groups of 3 or 4 people. The facilitator will ask each group a question about the food and nutrient combination they propose and give them time to come up with a range of ideas, regardless of the feasibility. Post-it notes and pens will be provided.

Validation

**90
mins**

Validation

Step 1

Lay participants will be asked for their views on increasing fibre and protein

Step 2

Lay participants will be asked to review the proposed products from the expert groups

Refinement

90
mins

Refinement

The researcher will present the findings of the validation to the experts and provide a written document with extracts of transcripts for context.

The experts will review the output of the validation findings and create a shortlist of feasible products.

Summary

**90
mins**

Summary

The academic team and the experts will summarise the findings and agree the format to disseminate the output

Ideation topic Guide

Introduction

Hello. My name is Barbara Bray. I am the Researcher for the Healthy Ageing Diet study. The purpose of the workshop is to define acceptable foods that would be feasible for target nutrient fortification and product development.

The workshop will be recorded, and the words written into a document for research purposes, but these documents will be anonymous and not contain your name. The recordings will be destroyed when the typed documents have been prepared.

You may inform me if there are any statements that you do not wish to have transcribed at the end of the session.

There are no right or wrong answers; just your opinion based on your experiences. There's no requirement to agree with other participants and it is fine to challenge and disagree. I would ask that we are respectful when doing so.

Any questions before we begin? **[Answer any questions.]**

ICEBREAKER (15m)

CO-DESIGN PRESENTATION (15m)

1. Review target consumer profiles (30m)

Participants will be presented with the consumer profiles of four people from the workbook and the summary of part 1 and part 2 of the Healthy Ageing Diet study (HADi). The facilitator will go round the room one-by-one capturing initial ideas that participants have about the food behaviours of the four people, using the information on recommended guidelines for healthy ageing diets and the feedback from the HADi interviews. This is a good time to collate any ideas that experts already have and stick them on post-it notes

2. Ask participants to group into themes and rate the ideas (20m)

The facilitator will then ask participants to group the ideas under themes. Each person will be given 5 stickers to allocate to the ideas that could have the most impact on fibre and protein, either because the foods will be eaten frequently or because the food is high in both nutrients. There is no minimum or maximum number of sticky dots that can be allocated to a particular idea.

5.

1

3. BREAK

The facilitator will hand out post-it notes during the refreshment break in case anyone has anything they remember once they have left the room.

4. Create insight statements from the themes (10m)

At this step the facilitator gets the group to form four or 5 succinct sentences about the food behaviours of the four people that will be used to generate ideas. For example, “the widow from Berkshire has a good breakfast but she is not having enough protein in it”.

5. Create ‘How might we?’ questions from the insights (10m)

From the insight statements the group will then be asked to turn the insight statements into ‘How might we?’ questions. For example, how might we get the widow to increase her protein intake at breakfast?

6. Pose the final question to the group to brainstorm (30m)

The facilitator will brief participants on the rules of the brainstorm to encourage a flow of ideas without restriction.

The team will be split into sub-groups of 3 or 4 people.

The facilitator will ask each group a question about the food and nutrient combination they propose and give them time to come up with a range of ideas, regardless of the feasibility.

Post-it notes and pens will be provided.

7. Group the resulting ideas into concepts (20m)

The group will collectively bundle the ideas together and the facilitator will collect the ideas to take to the next workshop for validation.

Healthy Ageing Diet Study

WORKSHOP RESOURCE 08.07.25

Barbara Bray

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Co-design workshops

What you will do

In this co-design project, people with a range of skills and experience are invited to create food concepts that meet the fibre and protein needs of people aged 65 years and older.

It's called co-design because everyone involved will contribute their ideas to the final concepts.

Overall research aim being addressed by this study.

The aim is to assess the feasibility of potential food-based solutions to optimise nutritional intake and support older adults to meet their nutritional needs. This will be achieved using a co-design process with lay people aged 65 and over and professionals in food manufacture, retail, public health, food policy and organisations supporting older people with food.

Research objectives

The objectives of the proposed project are:

- To engage key stakeholders in co-design workshops
- To define acceptable foods that would be feasible for fibre and protein fortification and product development using stakeholder groups.
- To gather insights from people aged 65 years and over, on their openness to increasing fibre and protein in the diet
- To understand which product concepts combining fibre and protein would be acceptable to people aged 65 years and over.

01

Dietary needs of 65+

Older people's diets are not providing sufficient nutrients to maintain good health with ageing. Increasing the missing the nutrients is important to support healthspan.

02

Changing food behaviours

The food environment including access, availability and quality has a big impact on people's behaviour in addition to knowledge and life changes

03

Solution

Designing nutritious foods that suit the tastes and existing diets of older people is one solution that stakeholders can work on.

Workshops planner

There are 4 stages to the development of the final solution

Ideation
EXPERT PANEL

Validation
LAY PANEL

Refinement
EXPERT PANEL

Summary
ACADEMIC TEAM

120 mins

Ideation

- Ideas selection
- Insight statements
- How might we exercise
- Brainstorm
- Shortlist ideas

Workshop scope

To define acceptable foods that would be feasible for target nutrient fortification and product development.

The workshop was hosted at King's College London by Dr Richard Siouw, Director of Ageing Research

Professionals

Tesco, Healthy and Sustainable diets manager

Nutrition Advisor to the elderly

Senior lecturer in nutrition, KCL

Senior Scientist, BNF

Dietitian and product developer, Apetito

Nutrition Manager, Danone

Project Manager, Dunbia

Editor, Food Manufacturer

Participants were asked 'what are your objectives for this session'?

Learning more on cross industry views on healthy ageing

Build understanding of dietary needs for a healthy ageing diet. Understand options and solutions that most appeal to consumers

Hear diverse views/opinions to try to solve a real problem. More minds are better than one.

Refocus on ageing population and understand more. Understand the experts view point on protein in the diet of the ageing population.

More insight into the issues for young old people. Make friends and new contacts

Meet new people and help those in the food sector discover new opportunities through the insight gathered.

Understand more about what changes are realistic for older adults to improve nutrition

**90
mins**

Validation

Step 1

Lay participants will be asked for their views on increasing fibre and protein

Step 2

Lay participants will be asked to review the proposed products from the expert groups

Validation workshop results

Two groups of adults aged 65 years and over
N=7 Northern Ireland
N=6 Reading/Berkshire

Protein and fibre discussion

What foods contain fibre and what would you eat more of?

- Common foods mentioned included cereals, bread, nuts and green vegetables
- Beans were considered with prompting

What foods contain protein and what would you eat more of?

- Fish, eggs, meat, chicken and cheese were the top foods, also protein shakes
- Plant based sources were mentioned with prompting

What foods could participant eat more of in order to consume more protein and fibre?

Responses from participants included -

Fibre – green veg, oats, nuts and grains, brown bread, Weetabix

Protein – participants mentioned oily fish, eggs, meat, chicken, cheese, protein shakes as sources

Participants mentioned not eating much of, and if encouraged, would eat more of: green vegetables, eggs, fish, red meat

One participant is unsure if older adults are really not eating enough fibre and protein. If they feel well and healthy and their bloods are okay they are going to assume that they are eating healthy enough.

Comments from validation exercise

Fortified ready meals would be great

I would buy fortified stock cube (Magicube) and use in stews and curries

I like the idea of the strength sprinkle in a shaker like for salt and pepper

The single serve is great for single people and there is less waste

I don't buy ready meals

I don't eat after 6pm – snacks aren't for me

Sous Vide reminds me of boil in the bag meals and I don't like that idea

I prefer to buy my own vegetables that have them in a meal kit

Key take-homes from the session

- The importance of understanding dietary needs for older adults.
- Protein and fibre are crucial components of a healthy diet.
- Innovative food concepts can enhance nutrition for older adults.
- Personalized nutrition solutions can address specific health concerns.
- Convenience in meal preparation is a significant factor for many individuals.
- Ready-made meals can provide nutritious options for those with limited cooking ability.
- Feedback from participants is essential for refining food concepts.
- Engaging discussions can lead to valuable insights in nutrition research.
- Understanding barriers to healthy eating is crucial for effective solutions.
- Collaboration among nutrition experts can drive innovation in food products.

Results of concept scores

Concept	Score %
MagiCube	85
Personalised meal kit – Nourish Box	77
Single supper sizzle	69
Sous vide – Young at Hearty stew	69
Lite Bite/ Nite Bite	46
Strength sprinkle	46
Yoghurt with Fibre topping – rise and nourish	38
Ready Meal with MagiCube	38
Yogo with opener	38

90
mins

Refinement

The researcher will present the findings of the validation to the experts and provide a written document with extracts of transcripts for context.

The experts will review the output of the validation findings and create a shortlist of feasible products.

In this workshop, food experts from various fields came together to discuss innovative food concepts designed to meet the dietary needs of older adults. From personalised meal kits to nutrient-rich snacks, one core solution aims to enhance the quality of life for those aged 65 and over by making the smallest of dietary changes.

What we did

The group reviewed the feedback from the validation session and discussed the top scoring concepts:

Magicube

Personalised meal kit – Nourish Box

Single supper sizzle

Sous vide – Young at Hearty stew

Ready meals fortified with Magicube

Refinement workshop results

Magicube

A fortified stock cube that can be used in industry or by consumers in scratch cooking

Meal kit component

- Supplied as a standard ingredient
- Tailored for a personalised meal kit to support a low salt diet, brain health diet, low cholesterol diet

Sous vide ingredient

- A fortification ingredient to boost the nutrition of meat or pulse based slow cooked ready meals

Consumer ready stock cube

- Protein based eg <10g
- Fibre based e.g 6g
- Vitamin B12
- Iron and vitamin C
- Folate /dark green leafy veg extract
- Probiotic and prebiotic

Key finding

The key outcome was the finding that older people gravitate to the concepts that require minimal change to their existing food behaviours and that they seek solutions for chronic health conditions rather than ageing.

Proposed solution – Magicube a fortified stock cube

This product would be a range of flavours and ingredients providing a few grammes of fibre and protein to boost the daily intake and a selection of appropriate vitamins and minerals and ingredients that support health.

It could be sold like an existing stock cube for consumers to use in scratch cooking or added to ready meals during the manufacturing process and these would be sold as fortified ready meals.

90
mins

Summary

The academic team and the experts will summarise the findings.

See notes on APEASE criteria

At any point where assessment of proposed or existing aspects of interventions is required, the APEASE criteria can be used to structure this process. APEASE can be applied to anything from a general concept to a detailed plan for a proposed intervention, or a formal evaluation of an intervention that has already been implemented.

Scoring system: Low, Medium, High

6 criteria – Acceptability, Practicability, Effectiveness, Affordability, Side-effects and Equity

We will look at 3 -

Acceptability How far is it acceptable to key stakeholders? This includes the target group, potential funders, practitioners delivering the interventions and relevant community and commercial groups.

Practicability Can it be implemented at scale within the intended context, material and human resources? What would need to be done to ensure that the resources and personnel were in place, and is the intervention sustainable?

Effectiveness How effective is the intervention in achieving the policy objective(s)? How far will it reach the intended target group and how large an effect will it have on those who are reached?

90
mins

Summary

The academic team and the experts will agree the format to disseminate the output

Dissemination

The results of the Healthy Ageing Diet study will be presented at seminar for stakeholders to attend, and a summary report will be sent to participants.

- What could this look like?
- What would be useful?

Lay group topic guide

Hello. My name is Barbara Bray. I am the Researcher for the Healthy Ageing Diet study. The purpose of the focus is to see what types of foods you would be interested to buy in the future.

The session is being recorded, and the words written into a document for research purposes, but these documents will be anonymous and not contain your name. The recordings will be destroyed when the typed documents have been prepared.

You may inform me if there are any statements that you do not wish to have transcribed at the end of the session.

Introduction

We'll go round the room and say hello

Types of foods that older people need to eat more of

The pre-workshop pack contained a summary of the types of foods that older people need to eat more of.

Which of the food groups shown would you eat more of? And why?
Which of the food groups shown would you not eat more of? and why?

Foods that are eaten regularly by older people that could have added nutrients

The pre-workshop pack contained a summary of the types of foods that could have the important nutrients added to them

Which of these foods would you eat? And why?
Which of these foods would you not eat? And why

Ranking

Please arrange the options in order of preference
Once you have finished, I will come round and make a note of the scores and combine them

6. MCEVOY_HADi_Lay group topic guide	Version 1	05.03.25
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Refinement session 08.07.25 worksheets

Healthy Ageing Diet Study Barbara Bray MSc
RNutr

Today's Exercis

01 Review the feedback for the concepts

02 Which key nutrients are missing / need to be increased?

03 Create a shortlist of concepts

04 Proofread and feedback

Concept template - HADI study

BIG
WHITE
BUCKET

Please draw/insert an image of the concept or the inspiration

PROT, VIT & MIN ADDITIVE - MACI-AD

Concept title - what is it called?

Additive for manufacturing that adds protein, vit & mins to any manufactured recipe dish.

Concept outline - what is it? Explain it to your audience

Increasing protein, vit & min in dishes without increasing portion size. Making products more nutrient dense.

What is the problem you are trying to solve?

Who's it for? Who is your target audience?

Older people lacking protein but don't want / or can't increase portion size

How does this concept solve the problem?

Adding protein, vit & mins makes a specific portion/meal solution more nutrient dense.

Reasons to believe: What makes this special?

Easy to add to many different recipe dishes. Powder is stable & long life.

Gut feel

Uniqueness

R A G

Ease of execution

R A G

Speed to market

R A G

Concept 3: Enhanced Ready Meals

Participant feedback

One of them asked if it is natural or chemical based

One of them, don't buy ready meals, they like home-cooked

Some of them, based on their lifestyle, yes they buy but preferred it to be fortified

Other comments – good idea for those who like ready meals, another said that they would be more likely to buy enhanced ready meals but they don't normally eat them

Another found the idea of fortification to be like 'additives' which would put them off. If anything is added it would have to be 'natural'

Concept template - HADI study

Please draw/insert an image of the concept or the inspiration

Please draw/insert an image of the concept or the inspiration

Easy Yago ~~Easy Yago~~ / Yogo

Concept title - what is it called?

A yogurt with a tool to help open pack, can be reused.

Concept outline - what is it? Explain it to your audience

Helping ease the pack opening

What is the problem you are trying to solve?

Who's it for? Who is your target audience?

Those with motor issues

How does this concept solve the problem?

Helps to ease opening with tool rather than relying on dig. ts

Reasons to believe: What makes this special?

Can be marketed towards young people too, those with long nails. Can become collectable, different coloured tools. Videos that can show Gut feel what else you can do with the tool

Uniqueness	Ease of execution	Speed to market
R A G	R A G	R A G

Pronounced yog-go?

Concept 2: Yogo - Easy Open Yogurt

Participant feedback

- One of them said, open tins and jars always have problem
- They always have problems with all types of packaging to open it
- One mentioned having Carpal Tunnel Syndrome so the tool would be ideal
- One said that it would definitely be helpful
- One said it wouldn't make any difference to them
- Most would buy it but it is not a priority

Concept 4: Magi Cube for Cooking

Participant feedback

One of them preferred it to be crumbly so she can adjust the quantity and add a scoop to help

Also like it to have different functions such as seasoning, boost, fibers, and proteins
 One preferred to have it in a shaker rather than cube

Generally liked by all

They were confused about which nutrient to be added as extra; however, most of them prefer it to be less salty

Concept template - HADI study

Please draw/insert an image of the concept or the inspiration

Concept title - what is it called?
Lite Bite or Night Bite

Concept outline - what is it? Explain it to your audience
A multipack of snacks that come in small portions - i.e 2 bags = correct calories

What is the problem you are trying to solve?
Over Snacking

Who's it for? Who is your target audience?
Those who snack too much

How does this concept solve the problem?
1 pack is a 1/2 allowance, so you don't need to ~~eat~~ feel bad eating more than 1

Reasons to believe: What makes this special?
The Night Bite idea gives the user permission for an evening snack

Gut feel

Uniqueness	Ease of execution	Speed to market
R A G	R A G	R A G

Concept 1: Lite Bite Snack

Participant feedback

- One of them has a 5pm snack time she has biscuit-based savory based.
- One of them She does not eat after 6 PM does not snack she did not like it
- One of them He does not snack for digestion issues
- Would need to be gluten free for one participant and available as either sweet or savoury
- Anything salty and nutty
- Healthy crackers with savoury dip
- Flapjack style and sweet
- Could include chocolate and sweet snacks

6

Concept template - HADI study

Please draw/insert an image of the concept or the inspiration

'Young at hearty' stews

Concept title - what is it called?

single serve sous vide stews to easily heat (High protein)

Concept outline - what is it? Explain it to your audience

widow isn't getting enough protein & needs easy way to make individual portions when home alone as low motivation to cook

What is the problem you are trying to solve?

Who is it for? Who is your target audience?

single occupants e.g widowers

How does this concept solve the problem?

High protein, easily individual option

Reasons to believe: What makes this special?

- Taste
- Tailored for need

Gut feel

Uniqueness	Ease of execution	Speed to market
R A G	R A G	R A G

Concept 6: Sous Vide Ready Meals

Participant feedback

They don't know the technology

They said it's fine. They can't try it, but one of them asked if it can be used for vegetarians.

Good for single people

Sounds good if it's kept natural

Not for me – I would just batch cook but good for people with dementia

Would be good for one portion curries – must have natural ingredients

Concept 7: Personalized Meal Box

Participant Feedback

They said it's a good idea most of them

And if it can be related to disease and help with doctors like hypertension, diabetes, bone or heart issues

Yes – provided I can have gluten free – would like fibre and Vit B & D, low calorie and low sugar (T2D)

Something that would help constipation/strengthen bones and taste good

Needs to be low salt/ lots of spice – helps with hypertension, high cholesterol, arthritis, weight control, Rosacea

Fat-free for high cholesterol

Improve bone health

Concept template - HADI study

Please draw/insert an image of the concept or the inspiration
 'strong start' ~~strong~~ 'Rise & Nourish'

High ~~protein~~ protein, nutrient enriched yoghurt with high fibre ~~hopper~~ easy to open ~~did~~

Concept title - what is it called?

High protein yoghurt w added calcium + B vitamins, not d ~~mix~~ a high fibre hopper (no added sugar).

Concept outline - what is it? Explain it to your audience

Convenient, easy to consume, breakfast options for increasing protein + fibre

What is the problem you are trying to solve?

Who's it for? Who is your target audience?

packaging designed for ease and convenience for older consumers but would be great for all ages.

How does this concept solve the problem?

All in one breakfast solution. for nutrient dense breakfast.

Reasons to believe: What makes this special?

- focus on ease of opening / packaging format
 - high protein + high fibre in one eating occasion
 - added vitamins.

Gut feel

Uniqueness	Ease of execution	Speed to market
R A G	R A G	R A G

Concept 8: Rise and Nourish Yogurt

Participant Feedback

- They already do eat yogurt with fibre so they were not interested
- One of them prefer to eat yogurt with no toppings or fresh fruit fruits maybe
- Great for those who skip meals
- Good idea but probably wouldn't buy it
- Not just a breakfast thing – also an occasional snack at any time (3 people said this)

Concept template - HADI study

* could be individual portion to be added or sold in a multi-portion bag.

Strength Sprinkle

Please draw/insert an image of the concept or the inspiration

'Golden Boost Porridge Topper'
'Strength Sprinkle'

Concept title - what is it called?

Porridge topper - blended mix of nuts, seeds and/or dried fruit to be scooped onto or mixed in porridge

Concept outline - what is it? Explain it to your audience

Low fibre/protein breakfast

What is the problem you are trying to solve?

Who's it for? Who is your target audience?

Older adults but would be beneficial for all ages.

How does this concept solve the problem?

Utilises a commonly consumed food and doesn't require any additional effort.

Reasons to believe: What makes this special?

Easy to incorporate and contains all of the nutrients older adults aren't getting enough of.

Gut feel

Uniqueness

R A G

Ease of execution

R A G

Speed to market

R A G

Concept 9: Golden Boost Porridge Topper

Participant feedback

They preferred more than the yogurt because most of them they like eating porridge

Concept template - HADI study

Please draw / insert an image of the concept or the inspiration

Single Supper Sizzle.

Concept title - what is it called?

Single serving, Hello Fresh type box for supermarkets.

Concept outline - what is it? Explain it to your audience

Single people not wanting to bother to cook for themselves or avoid large batch cooking.

What is the problem you are trying to solve?

Who's it for? Who is your target audience?

Single. Divorced. Over 55.

How does this concept solve the problem?

Cooking for themselves without buying in bulk + cooking from 'scratch'.
Can try new things without buying lots of ingredients.

Reasons to believe: What makes this special?

No ~~extra~~ waste.
Convenient. / simple.

Gut feel

Uniqueness

R A G

Ease of execution

R A G

Speed to market

R A G

Single Supper Sizzle

Participant feedback

Good idea if there is lots of variety – meat/fish/chicken etc

Useful for people who find it hard to cook

Like the idea of no preparation and no waste

One participant – unsure because of the unknown portion size

Another would like it if there is a good amount of veg

Select the ones which meet the nutrient criteria

Step 3 Shortlist ideas we want to execute.

Step 3: Add details.

What the ingredients and/or nutrients and other features that can be added to the shortlisted products

Name of Product:
Short description of the changes

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Short description of the changes

Thank you!

Appendix

Themes that emerged from the ideation workshop

Themes emerging from the workshop

Breakfast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oats – gentler fibre than whole wheat. Better for older digestive systems. Fortified porridge oats with ground nuts and seeds to increase fibre and protein and Greek yogurt – add dried fruit, pea or soy protein
Ready Meals	<p>Chocolate pizza</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appeal to sweet tooth but packed with ingredients that give fibre and protein <p>Beans on toast</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mixed pulses added to beans for higher protein option <p>Ready meal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One/two of 5 a day Source of fibre Lean protein Smaller portion/packs <p>Sous vide</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capitalise on the minimally processed technology to produce healthy ready meals
Meal kits	<p>Specific dietary aims</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heart health Cholesterol <p>Stew base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An easy to prepare base with increased fibre <p>Just add mince</p> <p>Curry Pack</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incorporate legumes and nuts/seed topper Can be added in addition to preferred proteins eg chicken/fish Increases protein and fibre <p>Sweet potato</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> with low-fat mincemeat and small portions jar of sauce to accompany Could do 65+ meal kit packs e.g. meals for one, quick meals on the hob <p>High quality frozen mixed veg/pulses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dark leafy greens to add to stews/soups when cooking

Snacks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protein/Fibre snacks e.g. meat crisps, chickpea crisps, bean crisps • Breads enriched with important grains, seeds and selection of different 'ham-like' options e.g. chorizo and healthy fats like avocado to offer variety • Could do a pack, with the bits ready done and easy to load onto a plate like a healthy picnic lunch • Multi-purpose dip/topper e.g. peanut butter to dip fruit in and then on porridge (less waste) • Finger food – packs of different finger food, cheese, fruit, crackers, cold meat and veg aimed at the older population rather than the <u>kids</u> version! • Drinking yogurts with soluble fibre and vitamins • Softer nut-like snacks for example sweet dates in a pack (maybe too sticky)
Small meals	<p>Fruit and veg filled options. Soups with added fibre</p> <p>Microwave rice pouch – add beans to increase fibre and protein – ease of preparation</p> <p>Make everything in smaller helpings. Fear of “waste” may put people off certain healthier foods.</p>
Ingredients	<p>Just minced – conveniently sized portions of meat minimally processed with added fibre/pea protein</p> <p><u>Mince meat</u> at 50:50 option combined with lentils or beans and used for chilli/lasagna</p> <p>Multi-purpose savoury toppers (beans/seeds etc) for eggs on toast and other meals</p>

	<p>Foods that are digestible – large amounts of protein can be hard to digest. What is the digestible format without being over processed?</p> <p>Pasta sauces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blended beans and nuts – easier to digest • Favourite flavours e.g. carbonara – white beans and cashews, cream of tomato – pine nuts, cashews and beans <p>Protein powder</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Added into mash potato/mashed veg (carrot and swede) • Mash potato within stews • Fortifying plant proteins with addition leucine with application to muscle health <p>Spreads</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthy fats with added vitamins/minerals and added fibre
Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protein distribution throughout the day. Breakfast a target for increasing protein intake. Bedtime protein feeding with casein (milk), a slow releasing protein. • Educating complementary plant-based protein blends/meats that contain all essential amino acids • Re-educate – healthy isn't low calorie • New labelling of product texture like IDDSI “ish” • Food labelled to solve problems rather than flavours – heart health/diabetic friendly/gentle fibre • Wholegrain or 50:50 – education piece that wholegrain options can contain 75% more nutrients (rice/bread/pasta) • Whole milk instead of low-fat alternatives – Greek yogurt – high in vit A, D and fatty acids
Miscellaneous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portion sizes and cooking methods suitable for small households e.g air fryers • Clementines etc too difficult to peel – need tool to help with this. Even 'easy peel' not good enough • Include a healthy ageing sections in supermarkets much like gut health – we discussed one example of where turkey used to be placed next to chicken in the supermarket but when it was placed next to beef steak, sales of the turkey meat increased • Format – ease of opening – smaller size – ease of opening • Access issues with prepacked cold meats, milk bottles, shrink-wrapped food, tins • Using frozen (fresh frozen) portions in correct sizes • Smooth texture – added nutrient dense sauces/gravies